

CREATIVE KOMPETENSIYALARINI THE ROLE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN FORMATION OF PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract: In this research work with the help of modern technology, pedagogical skill of the teacher instructs students to enhance practical training and organization. Modern lesson to prepare current status is characterized by the presence of important theoretical gaps.

Keywords: modern technologies, education, professional training, language, linguistically, communicative, cultural kompetentsiya, methods.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the system of continuous pedagogical education, which are the most pressing at the present time one of the main tasks, enhance the pedagogical skills of teachers and practitioners nazariyotchilar moral issues are called to enter into the system. The outlook for the citizens of new thinking and the problems of modern society to a high ethical culture requires nurturing. The modern position, and modern law 4-k method (communicative, kollaboratsiya, creative, critical) through fully developed modern pedagogical norms to know which is the ultimate goal of the educational process is an important component of the person. The modern education system of primary education in the process of learning that occur in the process from after the idea has been put on the basis of knowledge and ethical basis for a targeted primary school holds a special place. Coming of a new era with the coming of the third millennium is characterized relations with the surrounding society and the realities of this person, it means that it is necessary to build a new system. Modern realities of human relations is an important component of a fully developed person, which requires to think about the moral component. Changes in the system of education moral education in the context of modern society or the family does not become a problem. These issues are significant at the state level is in accordance with the form, method and requires you to work out the details of the approach [1-3]. Teachers exist who would carry out the task of modern education in our society about the person personally to the idea that ethics should be compatible. Modern educational technology in educational work in the system of ethical principles, knowing the rules of ethics and conduct is not always enough [4]. Realizing the importance of personal example in pedagogical activity, the teacher himself be to follow these rules, and ethics in relation to students and other people in their actions and must follow the rules of ethics. A conscious approach to this correspondence from the teacher to their professional activities and professional and from a personal

perspective, committed to the constant improvement of self requires.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

A teacher in the modern sense-at this high level, the amount of scientific knowledge have enough for a non-standard situation, who can accept, creative projects, which self-and business-savvy professional who is prepared to educate high civil liability for professional results. Realizing the social responsibility of higher levels of professional activity, teachers should continually push for the improvement of self-development and partnership. Also, in modern conditions we are free, independent, active activity to show the person we are talking about the necessity to educate the creativity in pedagogical. Many teachers and practitioners nazariyotchilar they will give enough attention to this component of pedagogical activity, without them the modern realities of the teaching profession it is to talk about the level of professional representatives who download [5-6]. The activity of the teacher, taking into creative from the perspective of its components, these components of professional kompetentsiyalar complex, especially for primary school teachers need to stress the importance.

The principle to be used in the primary grades 4 principles of brewing a new approach with its name we have 4 units includes:

Kollaboratsiya: Textbooks structured in a way which will help readers to develop ability to work in team. The students of this cooperation, sharing and mutual support to assist you learn the skills of effective thoughts.

Kommunikativlik: Students formulate their thoughts clearly obvious to the partner to listen and to understand the effective use of language tools and the delivery of information to learn.

Creative thinking: Students learn to apply new approaches to achieve their goals, innovative solutions and creative skills are developed will be able to resolve problems.

Critical thinking: critical evaluation of this methodology, readers information, and the review on

the formation of skills include the development of his mind. Students learn to approach the problem from the point of view of analytical and logical thinking, your own point of view on the basis of the shape.

A new innovative approach in the school before the introduction of uzbekistan, foreign experience was also studied. Singapore, china, england, finland, estonia, such as incorporating the principles of the country of advanced education educational we have 4 of the twenty-first century skills, pays attention to the development of the main.

PISS, like PIRLO, who hold high positions in the international ranking of state education "4K" including communication, research, creative skills and therefore they also have been active within the international rating given particular emphasis to like erishishyapti great results.

"4K" an innovative approach based on the model does not require special conditions for use in schools. For example, educational with questions and assignments critical thinking ability, communication skills while questions-develops through assignments and exercises. It is wrong to say that the conditions do not have to use this method in school.

To get used to the new approach mainly depends on the teacher. Therefore in the republic gathered from more than 300 teachers from coach too soon prepared. They helps in improving the skills of other teachers all over the country.

The results of a new innovative approach to student outlook, in the growth of thinking can be seen. Twenty-first century portrait is a student in the twenty-first century skills should be. The main purpose of applying the innovative approach is also the same. And finally, the main purpose of education to give students not only the knowledge, but to apply the knowledge forward in life is to teach.

Also, the importance of relations between teachers and students shaxslararo should be stressed. This relationship is at the stage of primary school for the children in the lesson set up a leading role in the process of practical importance in the process of training the teacher as a person belongs to. Every reader of primary school teachers in the process of establishing a personal relationship with ethical to comply with the norms and comply with them to have with their students should be an example. A partnership with their students teachers from the perspective of a democratic society in the

conditions of changes in the relationship should be. What, according to the teacher's pedagogical skills in topical issues of this stage is that more issues to consider with the realities of the teaching profession in modern society requires us to renew in accordance with the requirements of the new social. Teachers personal profession continuously self-improvement, to seek new solutions is one of the most creative professions that requires the results of activities and teaching will not always appear immediately. The need for continuous improvement of professional skills should be recognized by each teacher. Changing the conditions of truth and information in modern technology due to the development of self improvement-do not pay enough attention to the issues of the modern system of teacher education, which is difficult to be used.

The realities surrounding pedagogical skills to recognize, predict, and allows you to change; enhanced knowledge and tasks arising in the professional activities of the teacher and taken up by the process of finding new solutions to members in the form of these skills to summarize, the available professional kompetentsiyani continuous improvement; educated professional decision-making; the formation of independent professional skills. the position of the student. The formation process of the development of the teacher's pedagogical skills and personal resources to reveal the effects of his teaching is characterized by the ability to optimize at the same time, the educational environment of the "problem" allows you to give a decent answer. Constant development of society can't give a complete answer to the rapidly changing conditions pedagogical activity.

Practical activities for teachers, as his analysis shows, teacher pedagogical pedagogical practitioners always acceptable to make decisions in a situation that require certain conditions to work in and ready. Serious practitioners, teachers often can't make independent decisions, this requires serious skills and theoretical knowledge to practice. The design of the educational process of higher educational institution and the independence of teachers in practical activities requires knowledge of the theoretical amount that can be provided by very large, but occurs to a certain extent, these skills for a long time. In practice, the theory for young professionals who know well their professional activities on a permanent basis and there are cases difficult to make independent decisions on certain issues that arise from the teacher this skill or not, we are in the process of education can be gaps that we can talk about. In such a situation pedagogical component of the development process and the development of creative skills in the best way and their professional activities, self-reflect, the ability to provide that also. The formation and development of pedagogical system of education teaching excellence is based on the principles of advanced development.

Scientists as research shows, many teachers often full of stereotypes and stereotypes of professional activity of methodological, and this is impossible as the

development of teacher's professional identity makes rag'batlantirmaydi, but will hinder its creative potential. Accordingly, this future teachers to enhance their pedagogical skills of scientists, the computer's talk about the necessity of the formation and development of motivation on special operations work.

The development of the modern educational process and pedagogical defining a desire to increase the skills of teachers in the future, which indicates the need for the formation and development of a number of key factors should be noted.

First of all, the actual model of special education will remain at this stage of the development of society, this is mainly teacher-practitioners from the creative initiative, independence and its competitiveness, non-standard situations, the ability to act in the learning process of providing acceptable that will quickly take independent decisions. The formation of the creative potential of teachers professional it should be noted that depends on the degree of his thought. The level of formation of professional teachers in their work to the teacher thought to apply innovative methods, allows us to be active in professional sense, their professional activities, to reflect active not only helps makes you competitive and usually it increases the level of a specialist professional. Pedagogical activity-this is a process which is able to display the creative abilities of the teacher full. The options of this show talking about the teacher you need to contact the activity of constant creative search, in this case imagine that the teacher will not strive to perfection, developing, this is a bright example for its students. Secondly, the level of theoretical knowledge on educational sciences has significantly increased, the overall purpose of this process the teachers of the educational process and the future options, as well as enough skills to solve practical problems arising in the process of educational activities to the severity of the conflict between has helped.

Third, it should be noted that appear to be serious transformations in the education system. Thus, the process of diversification, the school and the practice of a form of the existence of new technologies in education, as well as a methodological framework for teachers of educational institutions, we are given the opportunity to choose themselves. At the same time, often high psychological-pedagogical education within the system of a sufficient number of independent decision-making skills to young teachers who have the theoretical knowledge acquired in the practice can't use, because of this experience requires certain skills. In the meantime, primary teachers to organize activities with the theoretical knowledge as well as practical skills in the educational process there are contraindications. In addition, in the process of professional activity, are required to display the qualities disabilities to practice a little bit creative. Novice teachers' pedagogical skills of the examples above, the increase of its self makes it difficult to educate.

3 THE RESULTS OBTAINED AND THEIR ANALYSIS

The importance of independent cognitive activity of students of teachers in the implementation of these skills available, leading to the formation of the necessity of kompetentsiyalari and abilities associated with it. This will help to improve the entire process for professional working in professional kompetentsiyalarni. In such a case, this knowledge and these skills to mobilize and filled out the form taken by the teacher, this will help to solve problematic situations that arise while. This professional teachers with the skills necessary and the form of the student's subjective position may constitute able to make decisions. Its creative potential of the skill the teacher researchers, professional intuition, taking inspired will show how that is directly related to prove this in general, the pedagogical talent" is called. His pedagogical activity of raising the qualification of the teacher is one of the necessary conditions should be continuous improvement. The environment in this process, which is called the environment, that is, teachers of educational institutions, its microclimate, and existing pedagogical traditions, a coaching system, the nature of the relationship between the personal and the leadership team members, as well as with each other, teachers play an important role.

CONCLUSION

Teach students: the problem allows to determine the possible directions for further research vector. Improving the pedagogical skills of teachers of moral education in the context of studying the issues of the promising directions of the head of the school of additional professional education institutions (in particular, the deputy director on educational work in primary school), additional education teachers, preparation of the improvement of the technology of teaching, new pedagogical skills and enhance the use of innovative technologies in the system can be retraining; located in a different educational environment and ethical education teachers the necessary skills in the fields of the study of the properties of the formation of (university, school and pedagogical skills increase system); development of educational and methodical materials on this issue.

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